

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Annotation: *Today, the younger generation is increasingly interested in learning foreign languages. Therefore, teaching a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of innovation, methods in the classroom. This article focuses on the effectiveness of organizing lessons using innovation methods in English classes in secondary schools.*

Keywords: *method, innovation method, institutes, technology, teach, effective, lesson.*

We will first consider the communicative system-activity approach in English teaching in general terms. This approach is to implement such a teaching method in which teaching English in an orderly, systematic and interrelated manner is carried out as a means of communication in the context of simulated (repetitive) speech activities in the classroom - an integral and integral part of general (extralinguistic) activity. The communicative system-activity approach involves a complete and optimal systematization of the relationships between the components of the learning content. These include the system of general (eg extralinguistic, pedagogical) activity, the system of speech activity, the system of speech communication (communication, interaction and mutual understanding), the system of English itself, the systematic correlation of mother and English languages (their consciously comparative analysis), the system. speech mechanisms (speech production, speech perception, speech interactions, etc.), text as a system of speech products, system of speech structures (dialogue, monologue, monologue in dialogue, various speeches and messages of speech, etc.)), system (process)) mastering the English language, the system (structure) of people's speech behavior. As a result of this approach in teaching, a system of knowing the English language is formed, implemented and functions as a means of communication in the broadest sense of the word. Given that such a system is used to teach English, it should also include the interrelationship of general activity motives with the communication motives and needs associated with it; subject of activity and methods of implementation; the typical conditions of its development

and the nature of the interaction of its participants (interpersonal, group), as well as to determine the nature, content and relationships and forms of participants adopted in this activity: their communicative, interpersonal and cognitive aspects, role, o Locations, areas, and English-speaking communication situations.

The main factors of teaching English are:

- 1) the nature of the impact of general activities on the content, selection and organization of the language of instruction and speech material;
- 2) modeling of communication situations in the learning process and methods of formation of speech skills and abilities among students;
- 3) ways and means of managing their educational activities in the classroom and independently with the teacher.

The options for a general activity for educational purposes, if it is related to learning, differ: real (educational), real (out of class), and potential (future).

The interdependence of activity units is of great importance to create a common activity basis for teaching English: operations, actions, and actual activity. Of particular importance is the concept of activity to organize the process of mastering the English language and the management of students' English speaking practice, including P.K. justifies the effect. In general, the systematization of general activity and the definition of its interaction with speech activity is carried out on a conceptual basis, developed by L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontyev, A. A. Leontiev and others.

Speech activity as a system is seen as an integral and integral part of the overall activity. Systematization of speech activities It should be noted that the types of speech activities that serve communication, including speech, listening, reading, and writing, are specific and interrelated teaching English speech training important for. The hierarchy of units of speech activity (speech operation, speech movement, and speech activity itself) ensures the process of forming order, systematicity, continuity, and coherence of speaking skills and abilities. The use of the theory of speech activity allows the formation of speech communication motives in English in the learning process and ensures that they are carried out in situations imitated in the classroom. Systematization of communication includes its communicative (exchange of information between partners), interaction (interaction between partners) and perceptual (mutual understanding and understanding between partners) content, structure and involves the analysis of interactions. Speech speakers and non-verbal means of communication (facial expressions, gestures, body movements, etc.) that are of great interest for teaching conversation in English are their national and cultural characteristics in the

interaction of speech. is to conduct an analysis taking into account. Structural forms of communication (dialogue, monologue, monologue in dialogue, conversation in monologue, polylogue), components of the act of communication (cycle, period, macrodialog), speech genres of communication (monologue-message, comment, argument, etc.). , dialogue (conversation, debate, question-answer conversation, reflection, etc.), the rules of speech etiquette and communication techniques adopted in English in certain social situations, as well as the repertoire and reaction of speech effects in various situational and thematically defined communication actions . Systematization of linguistic materials for the purpose of teaching conversation in English includes the use of phonetic, lexical and grammatical aspects of language, as well as a real systematic description of communicative linguistics and pragmalinguistics, functional grammar, contrasting linguistic data. Systematizing language as a means of communication must meet three basic requirements:

- 1) to create a linguistic basis for teaching English, taking into account the language experience of students and their knowledge of the native language;
- 2) teach them a specific (complete, abbreviated or selected) version of the English language system;
- 3) meets the conditions for the implementation of the communicative function of English in teaching and mastering it by students.

The principle of assessing their communicative appropriateness (V.G. Kostomarov) and the principle of active communication (A.A. Leontyev) should be used as the basis in the process of selection and arrangement of linguistic and speech material and the management of its skills. In addition to teaching different units of English - phonetic, grammatical, lexical, intonation (prosodic) - communication, functional statements, different types of speech interaction of interlocutors, functional superphrase unit, communicative intentions (intentions) of interlocutors speech implementation options, variable methods as well as communicative response, verbal communication techniques (including verbal etiquette), role-conditioned statement patterns, and more. The linguistic foundations of teaching communication in English should unite the whole arsenal of linguistic units and means of speech communication into one whole.

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